

Review of Wireless and Wearable Electroencephalogram Brain Computer Interfaces (BCI)

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Abstract – Biomedical signal monitoring systems have rapidly advanced in recent years, propelled by significant advances in electronic and information technologies. Brain-computer interface (BCI) is one of the important research branches and has become a hot topic in the study of neural engineering, rehabilitation, and brain science. Traditionally, most BCI systems use bulky, wired laboratory-oriented sensing equipments to measure brain activity under well-controlled conditions within a confined space. Using bulky sensing equipments not only is uncomfortable and inconvenient for users, but also impedes their ability to perform routine tasks in daily operational environments. Furthermore, owing to large data volumes, signal processing of BCI systems is often performed off-line using high-end personal computers, hindering the applications of BCI in real-world environments. To be practical for routine use by unconstrained, freely-moving users, BCI systems must be noninvasive, nonintrusive, light-weight and capable of online signal processing. This work reviews recent online BCI systems, focusing especially on wearable, wireless and real-time systems.

I. Introduction

Brain-computer interface (BCI) is a relatively new field of research that has been growing rapidly over the past 15 years. A BCI system comprises a set of sensing and signal-processing components that enables the acquisition and analysis of brain activities in order to establish a reliable, direct communication channel between the brain and an external device such as a computer or a neuroprosthesis system, etc. Figure 1 shows the basic design and functioning blocks of a typical BCI system which consists of 3 main parts: signal acquisition, signal processing and applications. The brain signal is recorded by electrodes placed on the scalp (noninvasive BCI systems) or implanted in the brain (invasive BCI systems). The signals obtained by these electrodes are generally obscured by noises and other artifacts including power line interference, electrode displacement, subject movements, electrode/wire contact, and physiological interference from ocular, muscular, respiratory, and cardiac activities. To eliminate these undesirable noises and artifacts is a required preprocessing step. The feature extraction and translation components (fig. 1) are to translate the acquired brain signals into measures indicative of some neurological effects of interest. The output of the feature extraction

component is so-called ‘feature vector’ by the pattern recognition community. The informative features are further translated into some control signals such as visual feedback to the user, a sequence of electric pulses to control external devices, etc. Two key issues related to BCI systems are data transmission and signal processing. Data transmission can be classified as wired or wireless. Many existing BCI systems have been constructed using wired connection to link all the building blocks. As a result, wired BCI systems are generally bulky and heavy; more importantly, they often limit the users’ movement in ordinary working or living environments. Such systems are thus impractical for realworld use (for example at work). On the other hand, wireless transmission technology including Bluetooth, radio frequency (RF) or other protocols can largely eliminate the limitations associated with traditional wired BCI systems. Today, wireless transmission capability is embedded in numerous electrical products such as PDAs, cell phones and laptop computers. Such a ubiquitous technology has already improved the feasibility of integrating signals into commercially available electronic acquisition, transmission, and recording of neurophysiological portable devices. Furthermore, given the recent development of real-time embedded systems and signal processing techniques, it is now practical to implement and perform sophisticated signal processing in (near) real time. As a result, next-generation BCI systems will be small, lightweight, noninvasive, nonintrusive, nontethered and easily and comfortably worn. This study reviews current BCI systems and particularly wireless, wearable and realtime systems.

Fig 1 : Basic design of BCI system

II. Taxonomy of Current BCI Systems :

BCI systems can be classified in many different ways. The presented taxonomy of BCI systems was based on technologies and transmission protocols they employ. Seven attributes are used to characterize these systems.

Transmission medium :

Transmission medium refers to the material substance used to exchange information between different components (i.e. between signal acquisition and signal processing, or signal processing and application) shown in figure . The transmission media used by the listed BCI systems can be classified into two categories as : Wired and wireless .

Target

'Users' refers to the group of people expected to use the technology. Most surveyed BCI systems are in the laboratory demonstration stage, using healthy volunteers or animals as subjects. However, some studies focused on clinical applications. Patient groups included in these studies usable voluntary muscle control such as amyotrophic lateral were severely disabled individuals who have little or no sclerosis, epilepsy, spinal cord injury, brainstem stroke, severe cerebral palsy, muscular dystrophy, and other serious disorders.

Sensor Placement

In this taxonomy, sensor placement is divided into 2 categories: noninvasive electroencephalogram (EEG) and invasive electrocorticogram (ECoG). In general, the EEG signals have a lower signal-to-noise ratio in comparison with the ECoG signals. However, it is still more preferable especially for normal healthy humans in daily applications because of its noninvasiveness.

Number of Channels

Channel number can be classified into single channel, 2 channels, 3 channels and multiple channels according to the applications.

Training Time

Before using the BCI system, training may be required in order for the users to effectively control their brain activities. the need for subject training can be minimized or as of the technology rising.

Target Activity

This consists of activities that the target population wishes to perform with the assistive technology.

Neurological Phenomenon

This attribute describes the phenomenon (phenomena) used as a feature(s) to control the BCI system. For example, many BCI systems detect and employ a positive to a less frequent stimulus. Another commonly used phenomenon is the increase in neural firing rates measured by microelectrodes placed on the cortical surface.

Fig 2 : Wireless BCI system

III. Wearable and Wireless EEG Monitoring

A physiological signal monitoring system would be extremely useful in many areas, provided it was portable, wearable, and capable of monitoring target physiological signals remotely via wireless transmission protocol. First, a wireless BCI system can dramatically reduce installation complexity, wire weight, and troubleshooting effort associated with traditional wired BCI systems. Second, a wireless BCI system would provide users with more freedom of posture and movement so that they can perform their routine tasks in real-world environments. Third, when built with low-power, miniature signal acquisition and conditioning circuits, the front-end of a BCI system can be integrated into a truly wearable device such as a baseball cap, a headband, or a pair of sunglasses to maximize portability and wearability. If wearable and wireless of applications for BCI will emerge. In addition, the lowpower EEG monitoring proves feasible, a much wider range integrated circuit design can also fulfill the requirements for long-term field operations. Figure 2 illustrates a general wireless BCI system in which the wires/ cables connecting the front-end signal-sensing circuit and the back-end data analysis unit are completely replaced by wireless transmission protocols such as Bluetooth or wireless local area network (WLAN). The following section reviews the systems listed in table 1 that feature wearable and wireless physiological signal monitoring.

Wireless System for Long-Term EEG Monitoring of Absence Epilepsy

Absence epilepsy is a form of epilepsy that occurs most frequently in children. Due to the subtle nature of its symptoms, episodes of absence epilepsy may often go unrecognized or misdiagnosed . Since EEG is an effective means of detecting subtle abnormalities, it is desirable to continuously monitor the EEG of epileptic patients. Whitchurch et al[1]recently developed and reported an EEG monitoring system for patients with absence epilepsy. The system utilized a Bluetooth personal area network that linked the front-end (an EEG acquisition system) and a data analysis system. This wireless monitoring system allowed EEG monitoring of

freely moving patients as they performed their daily activities.

High-Rate Steady-State Visual Evoked Potential-Based BCI

Cheng et al.[2] recently developed an online BCI that detected and classified steady-state visual evoked potential (SSVEP) measured with as few as 2 active electrodes. Twelve buttons illuminated at different refresh rates were displayed on a computer monitor. The buttons constituted a virtual telephone keypad, representing the ten digits 0–9, BACKSPACE, and ENTER. Users could input phone numbers by looking at these buttons. The induced frequency- selection. Eight of the 13 subjects succeeded in dialing the coded SSVEP was used to determine user button desired number using brain activity. The average transfer rate over all subjects was 27.15 bits/min – one of the fastest communication rates described in the BCI literature. The BCI system also employed a wireless transmitter to allow users more freedom of movement.

Multichannel Telemetry System for Signal-Unit Neural Recordings

Obeid et al[3] used WLAN to link the front-end data acquisition circuit and the data analysis system. A multichannel neural telemetry system capable of continuously transmitting 12 of 16 channels was demonstrated in their study. The system comprised: (1) a 16-channel analog front-end circuit to condition and acquire signals from implanted electrodes, (2) a digital circuit to process and buffer the digitized signals, and (3) a miniature 486 PC equipped with an IEEE 802.11b wireless Ethernet card to transmit digitized signals. Digitized data (up to 12 bits of resolution at 31,250 samples/s per channel) were transferred to the PC and sent to a nearby host computer on a wireless local area network. The device successfully recorded neural signals from awake-behaving macaque and owl monkeys.

Hybrid Bioelectrodes for Ambulatory EEG Measurements Using Multi-Channel Wireless EEG System

Matthews et al[4] recently developed a wireless multi-channel system for EEG measurements in operational settings. The EEG sensors were based on a hybrid (capacitive/resistive) bioelectrode technology that required no modification to the outer layer of the skin. In addition, the EEG system featured a miniature, ultralow power microprocessor-controlled data acquisition system and a miniaturized wireless transceiver that can operate for over 72 h from 2 AAA batteries. The system acted as a wearable and wireless EEG recording system rather than a complete BCI system since it did not incorporate any specific data-processing capabilities or applications.

Vibrotactile Feedback for BCI Operation

Cincotti et al[5] developed several hardware and software technologies to explore the advantages and disadvantages of using vibrotactile feedback and visual feedback to control an EEG-based BCI system during user training. The designed system used Bluetooth to

send commands wirelessly from the host PC to the vibrotactile apparent when the visual channel was heavily loaded by device. Advantages of using vibrotactile feedback became a complex task. Their study showed that users felt, after some training, more natural to interact with the BCI.

Summerising the BCI system as the BCI system developed by Cincotti et , whose wireless transmission lies between the host PC (intermediate stage) and the vibrotactile feedback device (back end), other BCI systems employed a wireless transmission module between the signal acquisition (front end) and signal analysis units (intermediate stage). Notably, all 5 wearable and wireless BCI systems mentioned focused on custom hardware and software for EEG/ECOG monitoring rather than on hardware for performing online signal processing. The acquired data were either recorded on a portable device or transmitted wirelessly to a host PC located within a confined space or on a WLAN. Analysis of acquired signals was carried out either online or offline using personal computers (PCs), meaning that the data acquisition units were wearable, while the BCI stand-alone wearable and wireless BCI that is capable of systems as a whole were not. The lack of completely high-fidelity recording and online signal processing could hinder the portability and practical usefulness of such systems in real operational environments. Given the recent development of embedded system and signal processing techniques, it seems practical to implement sophisticated algorithms in embedded systems for online BCI systems. Recently, Lin developed and demonstrated a wearable and wireless EEG acquisition and real-time data analysis module based on an embedded system for maximizing the usability, portability and wearability of BCI. The details are presented in the next section.

	References		
	1	2	3
Signal	EEG	SSVEP	Single unit
Channels	6	2	16
Transmission	Bluetooth	Wireless	IEE 802.11
Resolution of A/D	12	-	8
Sampling rate	-	200	244
Gain	10,000	-	500 / 1000
Filter	60 Hz low pass	4-35 HZ Band pass	211 Hz high pass
Signal processing system	Notebook	Computer	66 Mhz AMD processor
Analysis procedures implemented in the portable device	-	FFT	-

Table 1 : Comparison between wireless BCI

	References		
	4	5	6,7
Signal	EEG	EEG	EEG/EMG ECG/EOG
Channels	Multi channel	Multi channel	4
Transmission	-	Bluetooth	Bluetooth/RF
Resolution of A/D	16	-	8
Sampling rate	-	500	457
Gain	-	-	500 / 1000
Filter	-	-	1 ~ 100 Hz
Signal processing system	Computer PDA	Computer	Custom dual core DSP
Analysis procedures implemented in the portable device	-	FFT Gabor filter feature selection	down sample Hanning windowed FFT normalization moving average PCA linear regression model

Table 2 : Comparison between wireless BCI

IV. Real-World Applications of Wearable and Wireless BCI :

The wearable and wireless BCI system developed and published by Lin et al[6] featured dry micro-electromechanical system EEG sensors, low-power signal acquisition, amplification and digitization, wireless telemetry, and online signal processing. Figure 3 shows the pictures and the system architecture of the BCI system, which comprises 5 major units: (A) signal acquisition and amplification units, (B) wireless data transmission unit, (C) dual-core signal processing unit, (D) host system for data storage and real-time display and (E) warning device for providing feedback to the user. EEG signals were obtained using dry EEG sensors that did not require skin preparation and gel application to ensure good electrical conductivity between the sensor and skin. The acquired signals were first amplified by the signal acquisition and amplification unit. The wireless data transmission unit comprised an A/D converter, a complex programmable logic device and a wireless module. The wireless module depending on transmission range require- could be either an RF module (RF3100/3105) or a Bluetooth depending on the transmission range required. ments. The custom-designed DSP module comprising Bluetooth receiver, data processing and display circuits served as a development platform for general-purpose EEG signal processing. The analytical procedures implemented in the investigation included: (1) downsampling, (2) Hanning windowed fast Fourier transform, (3)

normalization, (4) moving average, (5) independent/principal component analysis, and (6) linear regression model. The procedures were designed to estimate subject performance and putative level of drowsiness (or potentially other attributes) based on the EEG power spectra. The BCI delivers arousing warning tones to the subject to maintain optimal performance in the study of Lin. Notably, the BCI system actually serves as a plat - form that can be programmed and extended to many other BCI applications.

Fig.3. Photos and block diagram of the BCI system proposed by Lin (A) EEG acquisition and Amplifying unit. (B) Wireless transmission. (C) Dual-core signal processing unit. (D) Remote host system for data storage and real-time display. (E) Warning device provides feedback to the user.

Dry MEMS Electrodes and Electrode Holders

The use of MEMS technology to build a silicon-based spiked electrode array or so-called dry electrode, to enable EEG, EOG, ECG, and EMG monitoring without conductive paste or scalp preparation. However, the connectors between the dry sensors and DAQ board were not very robust in the BCI-cap. This study incorporated snap-on electrode holders to house dry electrodes or commercially available EEG sensors.

Data Acquisition Unit

The data acquisition unit integrated an analog preamplifier, a filter, and an analog-to digital converter (ADC) into a small, lightweight, battery-powered DAQ. EEG signals are sampled at 512Hz with 12-bit precision, amplified by 6000 times, and band-pass filtered between 1 and 50 Hz. Fig. 3 shows the block diagram of the DAQ unit. Fig. 3 shows the DAQ unit for each electrode (20mm x 18mm PCB 'node'). To reduce the number of wires for high-density recordings, the power, clocks, and measured signals are daisy-chained from one node to another with bit-serial output. That is, adjacent nodes (electrodes) are connected together to (1) share the power, reference voltage, and ADC clocks, and (2) daisy chain the digital outputs.

Wireless Transmission Unit

It used a Bluetooth module to send the acquired EEG signals to a custom real-time DSP unit described below or a Bluetooth-enable cell phone which was used as a realtime signal-processing unit. The dimension of the wireless transmission circuit was 40 x 25 mm² (as shown in Figure 3). Figure 3 shows a picture of the integrated 4-channel wireless EEG system. A reference and a ground channels were also included in the system (not shown). The integrated circuitry can be embedded into a headband, NCTU BCI-headband, as shown in Figure 3. The power-consumption of the NCTU BCI-headband is very low (a 1100 mAh Li-ion battery can last over 33 hours).

Real-Time Digital Signal Processing Unit

light-weight, portable, low-power, and have on-line data receiving and real-time signal processing function. Therefore, this study designed and developed a real-time digital signal processing unit which used a Bluetooth module to receive the acquired EEG signals from the NCTU BCI-headband and process the EEG signals via its core processor in near real-time. The core processor is the Blackfin processor (Analog Device Incorporation, ADSP-BF533) which provided a high performance, power efficient processor choice for demanding signal processing applications. The dimension of the miniature DSP unit is about 65 x 45 mm² (as shown in Figure 3). The maximum high processing performance of the BF533 core processor can reach 600MHz. Furthermore, the following peripheral modules were also incorporated in the unit. To be practical used in operational environments, the signal processing unit must be

Data-Logging and Digital Signal Processing on a Cell Phone

To demonstrate the application of the wearable & wireless BCI during long and routine recording in operational environments, we have developed and installed a data logging Java graphical user interface (GUI) on a Bluetooth-enable cell phone. The Java program receives EEG signals from the NCTU BCI-headband and plots them on the LCD screen. We have also implemented power spectrum density (PSD) estimation using a 512-point Fast Fourier Transform (FFT) on the cell phone.

Fig 4 : The flowchart of signal procession on cell-phone

Real-Time Alertness Monitoring Using NCTU BCI-Headband and a CellPhone

Lin recently demonstrated the feasibility of using dry MEMS EEG electrodes, supporting hardware and commercially available TI DSP kit to continuously and accurately estimate the driving performance (putative drowsiness level) based on EEG data from four frontal non-hairy positions in a realistic VR-based dynamic driving simulator. This study implemented the cognitive-state monitoring algorithm on a Bluetooth-enable cell phone that received EEG signals and processed them with the on-board processor. The cell phone delivered arousing feedback when the participants were drowsy. Figure 4 shows the flowchart of the signal processing implemented on cell phone. Figure 5 shows the evident alpha activities when the subject was drowsy. We have also developed a user-friendly GUI to continuously track and display the cognitive states of the subject. When the subject was alert, the whole pie chart was blue. As the subjects became more and more drowsy, wedges of the pie chart changed from blue to red, increasing the red area as the subject became drowsier. When the subject became very drowsy, the whole pie chart became red and the warning set off.

Fig 5 : Custom GUI of BCI based cognitive

TABLE 1
COMPARISON BETWEEN NCTU BCI BAND AND BCI HEAD BAND

	NCTU BCI-cap [2]	NCTU BCI-headband
Dimension (mm)	 DAQ: 20 x 18 mm ² (4 pieces) Wireless Unit: 40 x 25 mm ²	
Weight	185 g	< 100 g
Precision	8 bit	12 bit
Sampling Rate	200Hz	512Hz
Bandpass Filter	1 - 50 Hz	
Gain	5000 times	6000 times
Output Current	480 mA	31.58 mA
Battery Life (3.7V, 1100mAh)	3-4 hours	33-34 hours

Lin reported a 4-channel BCI-cap which measured EEG and transmitted it to a commercially available DSP kit by Texas Instruments. This study extended the EEG recording system into a truly mobile brain-computer interface which acquired and processed EEG signals in near real-time. Table 1 compares the specifications and features of the BCI-cap and those of the BCI-headband. It is evident that, compared to BCI-cap, BCI-headband is lighter, smaller, more power-efficient and accommodates more channels with higher sampling rate and digitization precision.

V.Applications

- 1) EEG Bio feedback
 - Personal/self-improvement/meditation
 - Therapist-guided relaxation, etc.
 - Peak-performance training, "Brain calisthenics"
 - Adjunct to EMG, GRS, etc.
 - Treatment of ADD & other clinical disorders
- 2) Computer Control and Communications
 - "Thought-controlled" cursor, switch
 - Brainwave-controlled games
- 3) Entertainment, Virtual Reality
 - Control of music, graphics
 - Control of VR Displays
 - Interface to Light/Sound machines
- 4) Education and Research
 - Labs, experiments, demonstrations
 - Monitoring classroom/audience attention

VI.Conclusion :

BCI has recently attracted increasing attention. This study reviewed recent developments of online BCI systems, particularly focusing on the wearable, wireless and real-time systems. The main goal of designing and developing wearable and wireless BCI systems is to maximize their usability, wearability, portability and reliability in operational environments. Recently, several

wearable and wireless BCI systems have been proposed and developed. In the future, an increasing number of BCI systems capable of high-fidelity data acquisition, wireless telemetry and online signal processing are widely expected. These systems will provide further insight into the complex brain functions of users performing ordinary tasks in natural body positions in real operational environments. These systems will potentially have an enormous impact on clinical research and practice in gerontology, neurology, psychiatry and rehabilitation medicine.

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